

Supplementary Table S2. List of specimens used in phylogenetic analyses and ancestral state reconstructions via (a) BEAST and (b) IQ-TREE and R package *phytools*.

Supplementary Table S2a. Specimens used in simultaneous Bayesian analysis of sequence data (28S, COI, 16S and 12S) and morphological and ecological traits via BEAST, with number delimiting family (1, Xenophoridae; 2, Struthiolariidae; 3, Aporrhaidae; 4, Seraphsidae; 5, Rostellariidae; 6, Strombidae), species, sampling locality, collection date and depth, registration number, molecular data (GenBank accession number or 'NA', indicating morphological data only; dash (–), missing data), morphological data (Y, data available (method in parentheses); N, no data), eye (L, left; R, right; U, unknown), preservation (EtOH, ethanol; glut., glutaraldehyde). For molecular specimens with no morphological data available, another specimen of the same species was used (marked by asterisk, *). For collection details of the five specimens not sequenced in this study, see Irwin et al. (2021). Abbreviations: NHMUK – Natural History Museum, London, UK; MNHN – Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; UF – Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, USA; ZRC – Zoological Reference Collection, Raffles Museum of Biodiversity Research, National University of Singapore; MNCN – Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain.

F.	Species	Sampling locality	Latitude	Longitude	Collection date	Depth (m)	Reg. no.	COI	12S	16S	28S	Morph. data	Eye	Pres.
1	<i>Onustus caribaesus</i>	Off St. Petersburg, Florida, USA	27.7388	-84.6033	27.11.2004	156	UF 351181	OR9112 43	OR93 4417	OR93 4468	OR9343 68	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
	<i>Xenophora conchyliophora</i>	SW Marquesas Keys, Florida, USA	24.5037	-82.2580	20.04.1980	–	UF 26680	OR9112 57	OR93 4431	OR93 4482	–	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH

	<i>Xenophora pallidula</i>	Muttom, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu, India	-	-	21.03.2007	-	ZRC MOL.9417	OR911258	OR934432	OR934483	OR934382	Y (μCT)	R	EtOH
	<i>Xenophora solarioioides</i>	NW Paagoumene, New Caledonia	-20.4648	164.1283	17.09.2018	12	MNHN-IM-2013-84859	OR911259	OR934433	OR934484	OR934383	Y (histology)	R	Glut.
2	<i>Pellicaria vermis</i>	Waitata Reach, South Is., New Zealand	-41.0255	173.9075	02.09.2015	38-41	NMNZ M.318596/1	OR911246	OR934420	OR934471	OR934371	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
	<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	Orewa Beach, N Auckland, New Zealand	-36.5833	174.7000	20.01.2004	0-1	AORI YK#4036	NC_059921	NC_059921	NC_059921	MZ915630	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
3	<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>	E Isle of Arran, Scotland	55.5849	-4.9529	14.06.2008	103	NHMUK 20230924	OR911210	OR934384	OR934434	PP001795	N	NA	NA
	<i>Aporrhais pespelecani*</i>	Loch Spelve, Mull, W Scotland	-	-	01.09.1975	18-37	NHMUK 20190577	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
	<i>Aporrhais serresiana</i>	Málaga Bay, Spain	36.6135	-4.3718	11.05.2017	104-105	MNCN 15.05/95247	NC_059920	NC_059920	NC_059920	MZ915629	Y	L	EtOH
4	<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	Grand Passage, N Province, New Caledonia	-19.8300	163.7950	28.04.2008	31-36	MNHN-IM-2007-35460	OR911254	OR934428	OR934479	OR934379	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
	<i>Terebellum terebellum C</i>	N of Plateau Karembé, New Caledonia	-20.6267	164.2883	08.09.2018	0	MNHN-IM-2019-1737	OR911253	OR934427	OR934478	OR934378	Y (histology)	R	Glut.
5	<i>Rimellopsis laurenti</i>	Off Thio, S Province, New Caledonia	-21.5333	166.3500	04.09.2011	240-245	MNHN-IM-2013-64455	OR911248	OR934422	OR934473	OR934373	Y	R	EtOH
	<i>Rostellariella delicatula</i>	W Kairiru Is., Papua New Guinea	-3.3333	143.4667	19.12.2012	325-345	MNHN-IM-2013-18767	OR911247	OR934421	OR934472	OR934372	N	NA	NA
	<i>Rostellariella delicatula*</i>	Oman	25.5687 - 25.5500	57.3883 - 57.4187	25.09.1933	196	NHMUK 20190576	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH
	<i>Tibia insulaechorab</i>	Al Salwa, Saudi Arabia	16.8360	42.5840	19.10.2014-20.10.2014	0-1	UF 521337	OR911251	OR934425	OR934476	OR934376	N	NA	NA

	<i>Tibia insulaechorab*</i>	Red Sea	–	–	–	–	NHMUK 20230929	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6700	150.6800	28.06.2014	10–15	MNHN-IM-2013-55759	NC_059 925	NC_0 59925	NC_0 59925	MZ9156 33	N	NA	NA
	<i>Varicospira cancellata*</i>	Puerto Galera, Mindoro, Philippines	–	–	06.11.1914	–	NHMUK 1914.XI.6.284-288	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
6	<i>Canarium darwinense</i>	Darwin Harbour, Northern Territory, Australia	-12.4917	130.8967	16.11.2001	–	NTM P058594	OR9112 22	OR93 4395	OR93 4446	OR9343 47	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Canarium erythrinum</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.5317	47.4423	14.07.2009	46–54	MNHN-IM-2007-36698	OR9112 12	OR93 4386	OR93 4436	OR9343 38	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Canarium incisum</i>	Yagaji Is. Harbour, Nago, Okinawa, Japan	26.6100	127.9933	23.06.2017	Tidal flat	NHMUK 2019033	OR9112 21	OR93 4394	OR93 4445	OR9343 46	N	NA	NA
	<i>Canarium incisum*</i>	Yagaji Is. Harbour, Nago, Okinawa, Japan	26.6100 – 26.6517	127.9933 – 128.0067	23.06.2017	Tidal flat	NHMUK 2019035	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
	<i>Canarium labiatum</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6867	150.6900	06.06.2014	3–12	MNHN-IM-2013-47992	OR9112 15	OR93 4389	OR93 4439	OR9343 41	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Canarium olydium</i>	N Pemba Bay headland, Mozambique	–	–	15.07.2006	Mid-eulittoral	NHMUK 20060448	OR9112 19	–	OR93 4443	–	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>“Canarium” wilsonorum A</i>	SW Sainte Marie Cape, S Madagascar	-25.7617	44.8667	13.05.2010	40–41	MNHN-IM-2009-15840	OR9112 23	OR93 4396	OR93 4447	–	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Conomurex decorus</i>	Monseigneur Beach, S Madagascar	-25.0350	46.9983	27.04.2010-15.05.2010	0–1	MNHN-IM-2009-15860	OR9112 11	OR93 4385	OR93 4435	OR9343 37	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
	<i>Conomurex fasciatus</i>	Farasan Is., Abu Lad, Saudi Arabia	16.7977	42.1992	10.03.2013	6–9	UF 463278	OR9112 13	OR93 4387	OR93 4437	OR9343 39	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H

<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	Fusaki, Okinawa, Ishigaki Is., Japan	24.3650	124.1100	25.06.2017	–	NHMUK 2019039	OR9112 16	OR93 4390	OR93 4440	OR9343 42	N	NA	NA
<i>Conomurex luhuanus*</i>	Sesoko Is., Okinawa, Japan	26.6500	127.8750	20.06.2017	–	NHMUK 2019038	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	Asterias Hotel, Ayia Napa Marina, Cyprus	34.9816	33.9536	26.10.2017	–	NHMUK 20230931	OR9112 20	OR93 4393	OR93 4444	OR9343 45	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6600	150.6650	14.06.2014	2–12	MNHN-IM-2013-53759	OR9112 27	OR93 4401	OR93 4452	OR9343 52	N	NA	NA
<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae*</i>	Barag Is., Rempy Area, Papua New Guinea	-5.0183	145.7983	15.11.2012	Intertidal	MNHN-IM-2013-13445	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Euprotomus bulla</i>	Paquitequete, Pemba, Mozambique	–	–	14.07.2006	–	NHMUK 20060411	OR9112 28	OR93 4402	OR93 4453	OR9343 53	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Fusistrombus fusiformis</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.5317	47.4423	14.07.2009	46–54	MNHN-IM-2007-36710	OR9112 14	OR93 4388	OR93 4438	OR9343 40	N	NA	NA
<i>Fusistrombus fusiformis*</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.5317	47.4423	14.07.2009	46–54	MNHN-IM-2007-36647	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Gibberulus gibberulus</i>	Inhaca Is., Maputo Bay, Mozambique	-26.0733	32.9517	30.11.2011	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013-64491	OR9112 29	OR93 4403	OR93 4454	OR9343 54	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Gibberulus gibbosus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6250	150.7750	02.06.2014	10–14	MNHN-IM-2013-46767	OR9112 30	OR93 4404	OR93 4455	OR9343 55	N	NA	NA
<i>Gibberulus gibbosus*</i>	Kabira, Ishigaki Is., Okinawa, Japan	24.4833	124.1167	27.06.2017	–	NHMUK 2019042	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Harpago chiragra</i>	Okinawa Is., Nago, N Kyoda IC, Koki, Japan	26.5450	127.4600	22.06.2017	–	NHMUK 2019044	OR9112 31	OR93 4405	OR93 4456	OR9343 56	Y (histology)	R	Glut.

<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	NW Majunga, Madagascar	-15.4000	45.9333	12.07.2009	780–1020	MNHN-IM-2007-36711	OR9112 25	OR93 4398	OR93 4449	OR9343 49	N	NA	NA
<i>Labiostrombus labiosus*</i>	Betw. Nosy Be and Nosy Tanikely, Madagascar	–	–	21.05.2008	24–25	UF 423433	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Labiostrombus pulchellus</i>	N Kavieng Harbour, Papua New Guinea	-2.5783	150.7867	04.06.2014	15	MNHN-IM-2013-47346	OR9112 26	OR93 4399	OR93 4450	OR9343 50	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	Changi, Singapore	1.3095	103.9712	08.02.2009	–	ZRC MOL.289 7	OR9112 42	OR93 4416	OR93 4467	OR9343 67	N	NA	NA
<i>Labiostrombus robustus*</i>	Luong Son, 15km N Nha Trang, Vietnam	–	–	07.08.2001	10–20	NHMUK 20010428	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	Reef off Pulau Tekong, E Johor Strait	1.4367	104.0483	05.12.2016	–	ZRC MOL.283 54	OR9112 32	OR93 4406	OR93 4457	OR9343 57	N	NA	NA
<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B*	SW Pulau Semakau, Singapore	1.1976	103.7582	18.02.2009	3	ZRC MOL.291 7	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Labiostrombus variabilis</i>	Point N Plateau Karembé, New Caledonia	-20.6267	164.2883	08.09.2018	0	MNHN-IM-2019-1736	MW244 824	MW2 44824	MW2 44824	MZ9156 35	Y (histology)	R	Glut.
<i>Labiostrombus vittatus</i>	St John's Is., Singapore	–	–	08.07.2016	–	ZRC MOL.753 6	OR9112 24	OR93 4397	OR93 4448	OR9343 48	N	NA	NA
<i>Labiostrombus vittatus*</i>	Shoal Bay, Darwin Harbour, Australia	-12.2500	130.8333	20.10.1977	–	NTM P015366	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Labiostrombus wienekei</i>	Yomba Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.2450	145.7883	06.12.2012	20–25	MNHN-IM-2013-17824	–	OR93 4400	OR93 4451	OR9343 51	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H

<i>Lambis lambis</i> A	S Dumduman Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.0033	145.7933	09.11.2012	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013-12410	OR9112 34	OR93 4408	OR93 4459	OR9343 59	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Lambis lambis</i> B	Cape Bise, Motobu, Okinawa Is., Japan	26.7100	127.8767	21.06.2017	ca. 0.15	NHMUK 2019046	OR9112 33	OR93 4407	OR93 4458	OR9343 58	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Lambis robusta</i>	Society Is., Moorea Temae, French Polynesia	-17.4790	-149.7643	17.10.2008	12–30	UF 427893	OR9112 38	OR93 4412	OR93 4463	OR9343 63	N	NA	NA
<i>Lambis robusta</i> *	Society Is., Moorea Temae, French Polynesia	-17.4790	-149.8580	17.10.2008	12–30	UF 427905	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Lambis scorpius</i>	E Sek Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.0817	145.8233	11.12.2012	–	MNHN-IM-2013-18324	OR9112 39	OR93 4413	OR93 4464	OR9343 64	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Lambis truncata</i>	Inhaca Is., Maputo Bay, Mozambique	-25.9100	33.0483	11.12.2011	23–26	MNHN-IM-2013-64484	OR9112 40	OR93 4414	OR93 4465	OR9343 65	Y (μCT)	U	EtO H
<i>Latissistrombus taurus</i>	Hospital Point., Guam	–	–	09.08.2000	15	UF 282384	OR9112 50	OR93 4424	OR93 4475	OR9343 75	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6600	150.6650	14.06.2014	2–12	MNHN-IM-2013-53752	OR9112 35	OR93 4409	OR93 4460	OR9343 60	N	NA	NA
<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i> *	Fusaki, Okinawa, Ishigaki Is., Japan	24.3650	124.1100	26.06.2017	–	NHMUK 2019050	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (histology)	R	EtO H
<i>Lentigo pipus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6933	150.6483	11.06.2014	10–11	MNHN-IM-2013-51774	OR9112 36	OR93 4410	OR93 4461	OR9343 61	N	NA	NA
<i>Lentigo pipus</i> *	Mahé, Beau Vallon, Seychelles	–	–	2.1975	33–37	NHMUK 20230928	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H

<i>Lentigo thesites</i>	Banc Ouest, S Province, New Caledonia	-22.4460	166.4830	13.11.2017	2–11	UF 510153	OR9112 55	OR93 4429	OR93 4480	OR9343 80	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Lobatus raninus</i>	Borgnèse Point, Le Marin, Martinique	14.4500	-60.8967	09.09.2016	4–8	MNHN-IM-2013-72315	OR9112 37	OR93 4411	OR93 4462	OR9343 62	N	NA	NA
<i>Lobatus raninus*</i>	Jupiter Inlet, Hobe Sound, Florida, USA	–	–	06.06.1985	Shallow	NHMUK 20230930	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Maculastrombus microureus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6283	150.6700	21.06.2014	4–6	MNHN-IM-2013-55168	OR9112 17	OR93 4391	OR93 4441	OR9343 43	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Maculastrombus mutabilis B</i>	Monseigneur Beach, S Madagascar	-24.9417	47.1183	27.04.2010-15.05.2010	0–1	MNHN-IM-2009-15843	OR9112 18	OR93 4392	OR93 4442	OR9343 44	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Ministrombus minimus</i>	S Yabob Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.2583	145.7883	03.12.2012	2–6	MNHN-IM-2013-17612	OR9112 41	OR93 4415	OR93 4466	OR9343 66	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Ophioglossolambis digitata</i>	Choumare Islet, S Madagascar	-24.8367	47.1150	07.06.2010-09.06.2010	12–24	MNHN-IM-2009-15861	OR9112 44	OR93 4418	OR93 4469	OR9343 69	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	SW Horseshoe Beach, Florida, USA	29.3310	-83.3810	14.09.2018	10	UF 512221	OR9112 49	OR93 4423	OR93 4474	OR9343 74	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Terestrombus terebellatus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.5867	150.4850	16.06.2014	4–16	MNHN-IM-2013-54138	OR9112 52	OR93 4426	OR93 4477	OR9343 77	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Thetystrombus latus</i>	Bay of Goree, Thiwa, Dakar, Senegal	14.6117	-17.4483	03.09.2009	37	MNHN-IM-2013-50048	OR9112 45	OR93 4419	OR93 4470	OR9343 70	Y (μCT)	R	EtO H
<i>Tricornis tricornis</i>	Farasan Banks, Marca Is., Saudi Arabia	18.2206	41.3243	06.03.2013	5–15	UF 478460	OR9112 56	OR93 4430	OR93 4481	OR9343 81	Y (μCT)	L	EtO H
<i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	Kendec Is., New Caledonia	-20.6683	164.2567	09.09.2018	0	MNHN-IM-2019-1738	NC_059 923	NC_0 59923	NC_0 59923	MZ9156 36	Y (histology)	R	Glut.

Supplementary Table S2b. Specimens used in Maximum Likelihood analysis of mitogenome and/or nuclear data via IQ-TREE, with number delimiting family (1, Xenophoridae; 2, Struthiolariidae; 3, Aporrhaidae; 4, Seraphsidae; 5, Rostellariidae; 6, Strombidae; O, outgroup Littorinidae), species, sampling locality, registration number, GenBank accession numbers for mitogenome (13 protein-coding genes, 12S and 16S) data and nuclear 18S and 28S data (dash (-), missing data), molecular data (GenBank accession number or 'NA', indicating morphological data only; dash (-), missing data), morphological data (Y, data available (method in parentheses); N, no data), eye (L, left; R, right; U, unknown), preservation (EtOH, ethanol; glut., glutaraldehyde), absolute eye diameter, reference. Column headed 'source' notes whether molecular and morphological data originated from different specimens of the same species or sister species; data for some genera, e.g. *Tibia*, were represented by sequences from sister species (Irwin et al. in review), as no single species had both mitochondrial genome and nuclear gene data (NA, all molecular and morphological data originates from the same specimen). Data for *Aliger gigas* included two partial 18S sequences from different specimens. All sequences published prior to this study are listed with their respective publication references, with a complete reference list below the table. Most eye size data are collected from specimens listed in Supplementary Table S2a, duplicated here from Supplementary Table S4 for clarity; additional eye diameter data for species not included in the BEAST analysis were collected using the same methods. Abbreviations (if not listed in Supplementary Table S2a): NTOU – National Taiwan Ocean University; UNAL – Universidad Nacional de Colombia; LESGBCT, Laboratory of Economic Shellfish Genetic Breeding and Culture Technology, Hainan University, China; HAOFS, Hainan Academy of Ocean and Fisheries Sciences; TMBC – Tropical Marine Biodiversity Collections of South China Sea; OUC – Ocean University of China, Qingdao; CIBIO – Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos, Portugal; KBIN – Koninklijk Belgisch Instituut voor Natuurwetenschappen, Belgium; NV, no known voucher number.

F.	Source	Species	Sampling locality	Lat.	Long.	Reg. no.	Mitogenome	18S	28S	Morph. data	Eye	Pres.	Absolute eye diameter (µm)	Ref.
1	2 specimens (<i>X. japonica</i> + <i>X. pallidula</i>)	<i>Xenophora japonica</i>	Off Oosezaki, Suruga Bay, Honshu Is., Japan	35.0500	138.7833	AORI YK#4037	NC_059926	MZ920130	MZ915634	N	-	-	-	Irwin et al. (2021)
		<i>Xenophora pallidula</i>	Muttom, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu, India	-	-	ZRC MOL.9417	-	-	-	Y (µCT)	R	EtOH	383	This study
2	NA	<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	Orewa Beach, N Auckland, New Zealand	-36.5833	174.7000	AORI YK#4036	NC_059921	MZ920126	MZ915630	Y (µCT)	L	EtOH	350	Irwin et al. (2021); this study
3	NA	<i>Aporrhais serresiana</i>	Málaga Bay, Spain	36.6135 to 36.6082	-4.3718 to -4.3625	MNCN 15.05/95247	NC_059920	MZ920125	MZ915629	Y	L	EtOH	275	Irwin et al. (2021); this study
4	2 specimens (<i>T. terebellum</i> B + <i>T. terebellum</i> C)	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> B	Alexishafen, Papua New Guinea	-5.0900	145.8100	MNHN-IM-2013-12884	NC_059924	MZ920128	MZ915632	N	-	-	-	Irwin et al. (2021)
		<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> C	Plateau Karambé (Pte Nord), New Caledonia	-20.6267	164.2883	MNHN-IM-2019-1737	-	-	-	Y (histology)	R	Glut.	669	This study
5	3 specimens (<i>T. fusus</i> + <i>T. insulaechorab</i>)	<i>Tibia fusus</i>	-	-	-	NTOU NV	NC_065371	-	-	N	-	-	-	Lee et al. (2023)
		<i>Tibia insulaechorab</i>	Al Salwa, Saudi Arabia	16.8360	42.5840	UF 521337	-	-	OR934376	N	-	-	-	This study
		<i>Tibia insulaechorab</i>	Red Sea	-	-	NHMUK 20230929	-	-	-	Y (µCT)	L	EtOH	1492	This study

	2 specimens	<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-26.700	150.6800	MNHN-IM-2013-55759	NC_059925	MZ920129	MZ915633	N	-	-	-	Irwin et al. (2021)
		<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	Puerto Galera, Mindoro, Philippines	-	-	NHMUK 1914.XI.6.284-288	-	-	-	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH	542	This study
6	3 specimens	<i>Aliger gigas</i>	San Andrés Archipelago, Colombia	-	-	Sg300-UNAL-SAA	NC_024932	MW203300	-	N	-	-	-	Márquez et al. (2016)
		<i>Aliger gigas</i>	Florida Keys, USA	-	-	UF NV	-	GU198749	-	N	-	-	-	Spade et al. (2010)
		<i>Aliger gigas</i>	N Fajou Island, Guadeloupe	16.3542	-61.5847	MNHN-IM-2013-19530	-	-	OR933970	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH	1737	Irwin et al. (in review); this study
	2 specimens	<i>Canarium labiatum</i>	Wuzhizhou Is., China	18.3131	109.7663	LESBGC T NV	NC_084213	-	-	N	-	-	-	Li et al. (2022a)
		<i>Canarium labiatum</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-26.867	150.6900	MNHN-IM-2013-47992	-	-	OR934341	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH	888	This study
	3 specimens	<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	Hainan Province, China	-	-	HAOFS NV	NC_035726	-	-	N	-	-	-	Zhao et al. (2018)
		<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	Fusaki, Okinawa, Ishigaki Is., Japan	24.3650	124.1100	NHMUK 2019039	-	-	OR934342	N	-	-	-	This study
		<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	Sesoko Is., Okinawa, Japan	26.6500	127.8750	NHMUK 2019038	-	-	-	Y (μCT)	R	EtOH	1618	This study

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3 specimens (<i>E. aratum</i> + <i>E. aurisdianae</i>)	<i>Euprotomus aratum</i>	Ximaozhou Is., China	18.2394	109.3783	LESBGC T NV	NC_084214	-	-	N	-	-	-	Li et al. (2022a)
	<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6600	150.6650	MNHN-IM-2013-53759	-	-	OR934352	N	-	-	-	This study
	<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Barag Is., Rempi Area, Papua New Guinea	-5.0183	145.7983	MNHN-IM-2013-13445	-	-	-	Y (μ CT)	R	EtOH	1723	This study
2 specimens	<i>Harpago chiragra</i>	Xisha, Hainan province, China	16.7099	112.3519	TMBC 030691	MN885884	-	-	N	-	-	-	Liu et al. (2020)
	<i>Harpago chiragra</i>	Okinawa Is., Nago, N Kyoda IC, Koki, Japan	26.5450	127.4600	NHMUK 2019044	-	-	OR934356	Y (histology)	R	Glut.	2027	This study
3 specimens	<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	Penghu Is., Taiwan	23.5000	119.5000	NTOU LC-01-2020	NC_053786	-	-	N	-	-	-	Lee et al. (2021)
	<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	Reef off Pulau Tekong, E Johor Strait	1.4367	104.0483	ZRC MOL.28354	-	-	OR934357	N	-	-	-	This study
	<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	SW Pulau Semakau, Singapore	1.1976	103.7582	ZRC MOL.2917	-	-	-	Y (μ CT)	L	EtOH	1733	This study
NA	<i>Labiostrombus variabilis</i>	Point N Plateau Karambé, New Caledonia	-20.6267	164.2883	MNHN-IM-2019-1736	MW244824	MZ920131	MZ915635	Y (histology)	R	Glut.	1511	Irwin et al. (2021); this study
3 specimens (<i>L. sowerbyi</i> + <i>L. truncata</i>)	<i>Lambis sowerbyi</i>	Quanfu Is., S China Sea	-	-	OUC NV	MH115428	-	-	N	-	-	-	Jiang et al. (2019)

		<i>Lambis sowerbyi</i>	Great Koumac Reef, New Caledonia	- 20.6425	164.182 5	MNHN-IM-2013-84270	-	-	OR9340 23	N	-	-	-	Irwin et al. (in review) ; this study
		<i>Lambis truncata</i>	Inhaca Is., Maputo Bay, Mozambique	- 25.9100	33.0483	MNHN-IM-2013-64484	-	-	-	Y (μCT)	U	EtOH	2324	This study
3 specimens		<i>Lambis lambis</i> B	Sanya, Hainan Province, China	18.2394	109.378 3	LESGBC T-ZS001	NC_071230	-	-	N	-	-	-	Li et al. (2022b)
		<i>Lambis lambis</i>	Wenchang, Hainan Province, China	19.5167	110.800 0	OUC 21907	-	HQ8339 96	-	N	-	-	-	Zou et al. (2011)
		<i>Lambis lambis</i> B	Cape Bise, Motobu, Okinawa Is., Japan	26.7100	127.876 7	NHMUK 2019046	-	-	OR9343 58	Y (μCT)	R	EtOH	1528	This study
3 specimens		<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	Ximaozhou Is., China	18.2394	109.378 3	LESBGC T NV	NC_084210	-	-	N	-	-	-	Li et al. (2022a)
		<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.6600	150.665 0	MNHN-IM-2013-53752	-	-	OR9343 60	N	-	-	-	This study
		<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	Fusaki, Okinawa, Ishigaki Is., Japan	24.3650	124.110 0	NHMUK 2019050	-	-	-	Y (histology)	R	EtOH	2004	This study
2 specimens		<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	E Madame Is., Robert Bay, Martinique	14.6717	- 60.8800	MNHN-IM-2013-71190	NC_059922	MZ9201 27	MZ9156 31	N	-	-	-	Irwin et al. (2021)
		<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	SW Horseshoe	29.3310	- 83.3810	UF 512221	-	-	-	Y (μCT)	L	EtOH	1707	This study

			Beach, Florida, USA											
	NA	<i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	Kendec Is., New Caledonia	- 20.6683	164.256 7	MNHN- IM-2019- 1738	NC_059923	MZ9201 32	MZ9156 36	Y (histology)	R	Glut .	1724	Irwin et al. (2021); this study
O	3 specimens	<i>Littorina saxatilis</i>	W of Saltö, Sweden	58.8697 N	11.1197 E	CIBIO NV	NC_030595	-	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	Marques et al. (2017)
		<i>Littorina saxatilis</i>	Trondheim, Norway	-	-	KBIN NV	-	Y11751	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	Winne pennin ckx et al. (1998)
		<i>Littorina saxatilis</i>	Ursholmen, Koster Arch., Sweden	-	-	NHMUK 2011039	-	-	HE5908 11	NA	NA	NA	NA	Reid et al. (2012)

References

Irwin A.R., Strong E.E., Kano Y., Harper E.M., Williams S.T. 2021. Eight new mitogenomes clarify the phylogenetic relationships of Stromboidea within the caenogastropod phylogenetic framework. *Mol. Phylogen. Evol.* 158:107081.

Irwin A.R., Bouchet P., Harper E.M., Kronenberg G.C., Strong E.E., Williams S.T. in review. Advances in molecular phylogenetics of the caenogastropod superfamily Stromboidea: new insights from increased taxon sampling.

Jiang D., Zheng X., Zeng X., Kong L., Li Q. 2019. The complete mitochondrial genome of *Harpago chiragra* and *Lambis lambis* (Gastropoda: Stromboidea): implications on the Littorinimorpha phylogeny. *Sci. Rep.* 9:1–9.

Lee H.-T., Liao C.-H., Huang C.-W., Chang Y.-C., Hsu T.-H. 2021. The complete mitochondrial genome of *Laevistrombus canarium* (Gastropoda: Stromboidae). *Mitochondrial DNA B* 6:591–592.

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- Li F., Zheng J., Ma Q., Gu Z., Wang A., Yang Y., Liu C. 2022. Phylogeny of Strombidae (Gastropoda) Based on Mitochondrial Genomes. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9:930910.
- Li F., Gu Z., Wang A., Liu C., Yang Y. 2022. Comparative mitogenomic analysis indicates possible cryptic species in *Lambis lambis* (Gastropoda: Strombidae). *J. Shellfish Res.* 41:369–380.
- Liu G., Lao Q., Zhang C. 2020. The complete mitochondrial genome of *Lambis chiragra*. *Mitochondrial DNA B* 5:2373–2374.
- Marques J.P., Sotelo G., Larsson T., Johannesson K., Panova M., Faria R. 2017. Comparative mitogenomic analysis of three species of periwinkles: *Littorina fabalis*, *L. obtusata* and *L. saxatilis*. *Mar. Genom.* 32:41–47.
- Márquez E.J., Castro E.R., Alzate J.F. 2016. Mitochondrial genome of the endangered marine gastropod *Strombus gigas* Linnaeus, 1758 (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Mitochondrial DNA A* 27:1516–1517.
- Reid D.G., Dyal P., Williams S.T. 2012. A global molecular phylogeny of 147 periwinkle species (Gastropoda, Littorininae). *Zool. Scr.* 41:125–136.
- Spade D.J., Griffitt R.J., Liu L., Brown-Peterson N.J., Kroll K.J., Feswick A., Glazer R.A., Barber R.A., Denslow N.D. 2010. Queen conch (*Strombus gigas*) testis regresses during the reproductive season at nearshore sites in the Florida Keys. *PLoS One* 5:e12737.
- Winnepenninckx B.M., Reid D.G., Backeljau T. 1998. Performance of 18S rRNA in littorinid phylogeny (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoda). *J. Mol. Evol.* 47:586–596.
- Zhao Z.-Y., Tu Z.-G., Bai L.-R., Cui J. 2018. Characterization of an endangered marine strombid gastropod *Strombus luhuanus* complete mitochondrial genome. *Conserv. Genet. Resour.* 10:55–57.
- Zou S., Li Q., Kong L. 2011. Additional gene data and increased sampling give new insights into the phylogenetic relationships of Neogastropoda, within the caenogastropod phylogenetic framework. *Mol. Phylogenetics Evol.* 61:425–435.